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CAUSES OF DIFFICULTIES IN THE WORK OF A COACH

Khamraeva Zuhra Bahadirovna

Lecturer of the Department of "Physical Culture and Sports Activities" of the
Tashkent Financial Institute. Author

hamraevazuhro4@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

This article reveals the role and essence of a coach in the life of an athlete. Some of the difficulties trainers have during training with athletes are given also coaches with high level have skills that will help them in their work with athletes.

Key words: *coach, athlete, psychological factors, skill, experience*

Difficulties mean a subjective state of tension, heaviness, dissatisfaction, which is caused by external factors of activity and depends on the nature of the factors themselves of a person's educational and physical readiness for activity and on the attitude towards it. The feeling of difficulties may indicate the level of preparedness of the coach to solve a countless number of pedagogical problems.

The difficulties of managing the formation of personality are determined largely by the complexity of the interaction of elements of the pedagogical system, including the control (subject) and controlled (object) subsystems, which have unique properties and are influenced by interdependent social, managerial, pedagogical and psychological factors. Since a young athlete acts in the pedagogical process not only as an object, but also as a subject of education, control of the formation of his personality is possible only if the external influences of the coach coincide with the internal conditions of the development of the teenager himself.

A teenager's personality is influenced by many factors, the influence of which is difficult to fully identify and correct. This makes the process of personality formation partly, rather than completely, manageable. Due to the duration, diversity and complexity of this process, it is difficult to systematically obtain the results of control influences and identify changes in the development and personality of a teenager. Thus, coaches face significant difficulties when determining the level of education of young athletes. Determining the attitudes, feelings, beliefs, motives and needs of adolescents only by their statements and behavior is quite difficult and not always effective, especially since most trainers do not know the objective criteria for determining the

level of education, do not master the methods of pedagogical research, and do not realize the significant difference between the functions of leadership and management. Leadership is a broader concept, representing the rigid, normative external side of the organization of the educational process, while management presupposes the regulation of the interaction of the system of relations in the process of activity and communication and educational influences, taking into account the patterns and characteristics of the formation of the personality of a young athlete. To understand your functions, according to coaches of a high level of skill, is possible only by constantly analyzing your own activities and the activities of the children's sports team.

Difficulties in the activities of a coach are due to many reasons, which can be divided into two groups:

1) Objective (lack of free time to work with teenagers; insufficient assistance from managers of sports and mass work, administration, house management, Komsomol, sports organizations, etc.; lack of coordination in work with children between sports and Komsomol organizations, public education and housing authorities' public utilities; lack of material resources, sports equipment, sports grounds and facilities);

2) Subjective (poor knowledge of sports, as well as pedagogy and psychology of children, poor knowledge of a specific sport; inability to organize a wide range of the public and parents to work with children; low level of planning and conduct of classes; inability to conduct competitions at a high organizational level; lack of purposeful year-round work). Accordingly, the difficulties themselves are divided into subjective and objective. This division is advisable because difficulties are overcome in different ways. It is possible to overcome subjective difficulties only if you have certain knowledge, skills and abilities in solving this type of special and educational problems, and a high level of skill. Objective difficulties are overcome when the coach intensifies all sports activities in the community and uses all potential opportunities. In terms of the development of specific sports and pedagogical skills and methods of effectively solving pedagogical problems, especially organizational and communicative ones, master coaches of group II are higher than master coaches. Group I, this is due to the fact that Group I coaches often use stereotypical, taking into account the specific conditions of mass sports work. They do not show innovation in searching for ways of pedagogical influence; they use prepared methods for organizing the educational and training process, which, as a rule, do not take into account the specific working conditions of the trainer, the level of development children's sports team and existing forms of mass sports work among children and adolescents. In addition, group I coaches, introducing new forms and methods of working with young athletes, set themselves only tactical tasks, without correlating them with strategic tasks and super-tasks. Paradoxically, the methods of teaching specific sports skills often used in their

pedagogical practice hinder progress in teaching young athletes motor actions. This can be explained by incorrectly formed ideas among the coaches of group I about the methods of explaining sports exercises. Group II coaches do not have all these shortcomings. Their advantage is also due to the fact that they systematically engage in self-education, in search of rational methods of pedagogical influence, they turn to the experience of the best trainers and introduce into practice effective forms and methods of training, gleaned from special literature.

We have found that the satisfaction with their work among coaches of group II is higher than that of coaches of I. Representatives of group II motivate their activities by the need for self-expression in a new type of work, the desire to make a personal contribution to the process of identifying sports talents, to the mass participation of adolescents in active sports. At the same time, group I coaches are dominated by motives that correspond to the goals of their professional activities at school: to select and prepare the most capable children for top-rank competitions. In teams led by such coaches, there is no place for teenagers with low and average levels of physical fitness.

Group I coaches, as a rule, evaluate the results of competitions from the standpoint of their prestige, without taking into account the mood of the team, its attitude towards this competition, as well as the growth prospects of individual young athletes. Coaches of group II consider the sporting achievements of their team through the prism of the achievements of each young athlete, which are the result of the sporting goals set on the eve of the competition

Group II consists mainly of coaches, who are distinguished by innovation in production activities at the enterprise (institution), an interested attitude towards the social life of the teams in which they work, as well as the constant improvement of sportsmanship. They were or are actively involved in sports, react sharply to any manifestations of antisocial behavior of adolescents by organizing sports activities, and strive to make a feasible contribution to the moral education of the younger generation. They overcome difficulties in their activities, not only by identifying the reasons for the lack of development of specific sports skills in adolescents, but above all by studying young athletes and eliminating the subjective causes of difficulties, expanding and deepening knowledge, developing sports and pedagogical skills and abilities.

Regardless of belonging to one group or another, at the beginning of their activities, coaches experience the greatest difficulties, which we have systematized in this sequence.

1. Errors caused by insufficient general and “technical” preparation of a novice coach for independent work: insufficient knowledge of a specific sport and methods of teaching it; inability to manage one’s mental states, especially in difficult competition conditions; lack of communication skills; untrained diction, gestures, facial

expressions, movements, etc.; inability to act correctly in emerging situations; slow reaction, absent-mindedness during training; stiffness.

2. Mistakes associated with a novice coach's overestimation of his strengths and capabilities: self-confidence; arrogance, failure to accept advice and recommendations from experienced trainers; formal performance of their duties; categorical judgments.

3. Mistakes associated with establishing relationships with young athletes and restructuring them in accordance with the development of students: inattention to poorly prepared young athletes; lack of self-confidence, in the correctness of one's behavior in certain situations: ignorance of the psychology of childhood, lack of understanding of the reasons for this or that action of the pupil; failure to keep promises made to adolescents; excessive pickiness, excessive severity in relation to children; Constant complaints about teenagers to parents, class teacher, teachers.

4. Mistakes related to relationships with colleagues, school administrations, housing offices, sponsoring enterprises, parents of students: disrespect for the experience and findings of their colleagues, physical education teachers; tactlessness in dealing with children's parents and housing office administration; disdain for sports traditions; discussing the actions of parents in the presence of teenagers; ingratitude for the help provided by parents, teachers, etc.

5. Errors associated with the insufficient level of education and general culture of the coach: failure to fulfill one's direct responsibilities; lack of initiative and creativity in work; indiscipline; violation of norms and rules of etiquette; the desire to gain authority among students, their parents, and the housing office administration at any cost.

These mistakes in the work of a novice coach are not inevitable. Many trainers show examples of teaching work already in the first years of independent work. In addition, mistakes can be avoided if you know how to overcome them. As you get into the activity, the number of difficulties, in principle, does not decrease, but with the accumulation of experience in organizational work, skills and abilities, and depending on the personal qualities of the coach, the nature of these difficulties changes. The results of our study showed that coaches experience difficulties in all components of the activity. In total, the trainers named 149 difficulties that they believe they have to face in the process of teaching. However, coaches of different skill levels have different ratios of difficulties across components. Coaches of low skill levels, 44% experience difficulties in the constructive component, 23% in the communicative component, and 23% in the gnostic component (difficulties are not indicated in the organizational component). Trainers of average skill level experience 55.4% of difficulties in the constructive component, 14% in the gnostic component, 23% in the communicative component and 6.6% in the organizational one. Trainers with a high level of skill have

33.4% of difficulties in the constructive component, 33% in the gnostic component, 19% in the communicative component, and 25% in the organizational component.

With experience, the nature of difficulties in communicative and organizational activities changes most noticeably. To a lesser extent this affects difficulties in gnostic activity. However, in this area, experience determines the reasons for difficulties in analyzing the educational and training process and the results of one's work. Less experienced coaches either do not have enough time for such an analysis, or they need help from the parents of their students, the school, and the public. More experienced trainers cite subjective reasons ("I haven't mastered the skill," "I didn't attach importance to it before," "I can do better"), which indicates great demands on themselves and their work. Thus, at the beginning of their activities, coaches feel mainly organizational difficulties caused by the qualitatively new functions for them of the organizer of mass sports work among children and adolescents and the leader of a children's sports team. Their work is aimed primarily at organizing current events. Gnostic activity remains on the sidelines, since the lack of knowledge and skills does not allow it to be successfully implemented. Trainers of high skill level value constructive skills most highly, as they consider planning and coordination work to be the basis for the rhythmic functioning of the system. The largest number of significant correlations were identified between the level of development of gnostic skills and assessments of difficulties in constructive and organizational activities, which indicates the leading role of the gnostic component in the structure of the trainer's activity.

Thus, the analysis of difficulties in the activities of trainers made it possible to identify a number of trends. Firstly, trainers evaluate the visible results of their work much higher than the level of development of the skills necessary for the successful implementation of this activity. Secondly, coaches of different skill levels experience different difficulties in solving diverse pedagogical problems.

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